

A Study on E-Shopping Compulsive Buying Behaviour

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Introduction

The consumer behavior is ultimately based on the buying behavior of the customer, whereas the customer plays three vital roles of user, payer, and buyer. Consumer behavior is not that easy to predict. The retailing relationship is the dominating strength of customer buying behavior. The key factor of consumer behavior are customer retention, customer engagement, customization according to the taste of customer, customization, and one to one marketing.

Online Markets & Consumer Marketing

The online market and consumer marketing trends are changing in the current era. The earning capacity of every individual has been increased gradually amongshoppers. It create an positive impact on their way of buying. Most of the women in India are working. The structure of the family has changed according to the demand for family benefit. Even their way of shopping has completely changed and they are looking forward to the mode of purchase through online or any other medium of e-marketing. This rapid change is because of the time constraint of the consumers. They are looking forward to the better service from online retailers and consumer focusing on good quality and variety of products and expecting more choice to pick one product at the best price. So consumers take e-shopping as theirshopping medium.

E-shopping Compulsive Buying Behavior

The emergence of social media marketing influencing the customers to do compulsive shopping without any reason behind the shopping. Those days customers shop with the motive. Online shopping is alsoone of the stress buster to the customer. Customers do window shopping in the middle of their work time.

Online shopping considered has hobby and mood lifter for the people who fall in stress. If the compulsion is not mentioned then in retail terms, it has been jokingly known as retail therapy. Online shoppers engage in compulsive buying whenever their mood is not

fine, big billion days, exclusive offers etc. And also it happens at the customer's excitement or pressure of buying. They buy huge and they never use the product. This is called as oniomania or compulsive shopping.

Factors Influencing Compulsive Buying

Compulsive buying are categorized into socio-cultural, psychological, psychiatric and theological domains. Compulsive buying behavior is divided into two categories external and internal. Consumer buying is rationalized by using the self-regulation mechanism. The potential buyers undergoes the process of self-observation, judgment, and self-regulation. The self-observation is observing the one's action to provide diagnostic information about the collision behavior and fulfilling consumer goals. In the process of judgement, the personal standards, social comparisons done. The self-reaction is the process of observing an individual and judged to motivate other things from personal or social standards of conduct. Unplanned purchase may cast back ineffective self-reactive control. The factors are window shopping, purchase addiction, advertisements, offers, branded goods, food products, cultural factors, etc.,

Symptoms of Compulsive Shoppers

Shopaholics, feel sick if they don't shop often. Shoppers go out and buy, to make them to feel high or get a rush just like a drug addict. Shopping addiction affects more women than men. Consumers often buy things which they don't need. Seasonal market and holiday seasons may trigger shopping addicts who are not compulsive buyers rest of the year. Purchase addicts go on shopping all over the year and may they may feel little compulsive about buying few items such as clothes, accessories, sandals, kitchen items etc.,

Ways to Overcome Compulsive Buying

- Every single individual is potential shopaholic. In times the urge to spend money on shopping cannot be controlled. It gives thrill for those moments and then subside as fast as that make to realize that bought unwanted things.
- Most of the women confess that binging on brand new dress or a pair of shoes puts them in a fair mood. By that time they return from their shopping binge, they have elapsed the frustration or dissatisfaction which worried them.
- Neurotic symptoms may arise in among people from time to time. Shopping at the smallest amount excitement becomes an obsession.
- Find pleasurable pastimes to work off stress. Music, gardening, painting, writing, yoga are some of the happenings that can take your mind off stress.

Statement of Problem

- Compulsive buying is common in materialistic culture and the behavior can be as different to stop as any other compulsion or addiction.
- Compulsive buying is a psychological disorder where one experiences an uncontrollable urge to buy. Failing to act on this urge creates increasing tension that only dissipates with buying.
- Often the urge is triggered by undesirable events in moods. Eventually this behavior leads to harmful consequence for this individual.
- Countless compulsive buyers on no occasion they don't use the items they buy. Therefore, compulsive buying seems to be more about obtaining short-term relief from negative emotional state than about a desire for specific goods.

Objective of the Study

- To investigate the determinants of compulsive buying behavior of the shoppers
- To study the age group, qualification, annual income of compulsive buyers.
- To study the dominating gender of compulsive buyers
- To investigate the association between gender and compulsive buying behavior
- To investigate the association between the occupation and compulsive buying behavior

Review of Literature

Maria Michelle Morrison (2015) examined the various terminology used to describe deviant consumer behavior and distinguishes compulsive buying from the other labels. The research on this behavior examines in-store purchasing; the paper recognizes the possible problem of compulsive buying behavior occurring through the use of various media, such as the Internet.

Marju Raudseppa and Oliver Partsb (2014) found in their research are conducted about compulsive buying in Estonia. Compulsive buying can lead consumers into worst consequences: rising debts and financial difficulties, bad relations with relatives, and even eating disorders. The current research purpose is to find out how many people are affected by compulsive buying in Estonia and what factors are influencing that phenomenon. The research revealed that 8% of the respondents were compulsive consumers. Obsessive behavior is mostly influenced by materialistic factors.

Shoham Yossi Gavish Sigal Seg (2014) in his study that they examine a model to study the level to which drivers of compulsive and impulsive buying behavior overlay. Investigation results from 336 Israeli and 595 U.S. customers signpost the personality experiences envy, low self-confidence, and imagining normally drive the user characters of impulsiveness and compulsiveness, however some alterations exist between consumers in the U.S. and Israel. However, artistic alignments were originate to be unimportant in lashing qualities of suddenness or compulsiveness.

Paul Rose and Daniel J. Segrist (2013) says that the study is conjectured both positive and negative urgency would independently account for similar amounts of variance in compulsive buying. It is high and dry on the forecast of the statement that impetuous activities can be absolutely reinforced (e.g., by feeling exhilarated) nevertheless of whether they are incited by negative or rash actions made in response to either positive or negative moods are reinforced, they might be recurring and become habitual.

Rajagopal (2012) analyzed in the research that the motorists of compulsive buying behavior persuaded by store-based advancement over an pragmatic inquiry in Mexico. The buying behavior in position to the point-of-sales promotions existing by transaction firms and the factors of sensitivity towards motivating shopping arousal and satisfaction among patrons in command to figure store trustworthiness have been conversed in the paper. The researcher also builds influences around the convergence of allure of point-of-sales elevations and the effectiveness of customer services as a tool for fast a competitive lead in the retail business environment. The results specify that point-of-sales promotional programs have develop the principal tool of transaction in Mexico in directive to obtain new customers and retain loyal customers. They also found during the study that loyal customers are attracted to the store brands during the promotional offers while new shoppers are price sensitive and are attracted by the in-store ambiance of sales promotions and volume discounts.

Research Methodology

The research methodology is a way to solve a research problem. The purpose of this section is to elucidate approaches used in carrying out this research, how the research philosophies follow, then research Approach, research design, and the chosen research strategy.

Sources of Data: Primary data and secondary data collection method has been used in this study. In this research, the primary data have been collect through a well-designed questionnaire.

Size of Sample: The sample size is 263 respondents.

Sample Unit: In this study, data will be collected from the shoppers. Therefore for the survey, the samplingunits were consumers.

Statistical Tools:

Percentage Analysis: Percentage analysis is used in this study to identify the socio-economic profiles of the respondents

Chi-Square: X2 analysis applied to determine the association between the influence of e-shopping compulsive buying and socio-economic profile of the respondents.

Table 1: Socio-Economic Profile of the Respondents (N = 263)

Socio-Economic Profile	Frequency (%)
Age Group	
Below 25 Years	166 (63.1)
26 – 40 Years	80 (30.4)
Above 40 Years	17 (6.5)
Gender	
Male	135 (51.3)
Female	128 (48.7)
Level of Education	
Below SSLC	3 (1.1)
SSLC	2 (0.8)
HSC/Diploma	3 (1.1)
UG	94 (35.7)
PG	127 (48.3)
Professional Degree	34 (12.9)
Marital Status	
Single	199 (75.7)
Married	64 (24.3)
Family Annual Income	
Below Rs.2,00,000	86 (32.7)
Rs. 2,00,001 – Rs. 5,00,000	140 (53.2)
Above Rs. 5,00,000	37 (14.1)

The study found that 63.5% belong to the age group below 25 years group, followed by 30.4% belongs to above 26-40 years group, 6.5% belongs to above 40 years group.51.3% are male, followed by 48.7% female. 48.3% belong to the educational qualification of PG, 35.7% belong to UG, 12.9% belong to the professional degree, 1.1% belong to higher secondary/diploma, 1.1% belongs to below SSLC, and 0.8% belongs to SSLC educational qualification categories. The marital status shows that as75.5% is single and, the remaining 24.3% is married. 53.2% belongs to the annual income of 2,00,000-5,00,000, followed by 32.7% belongs to income of below 2,00,000, and 14.1% belongs to above 5,00,000.

Association between gender and E-shopping compulsive buying behavior

H0: There is no association between the gender and e-shopping compulsive buying behaviors

Table 2: Association between gender and E-shopping compulsive buying behavior

Gender	Consumer Type				Total	Chi-Square Value (P-Value)
	Brand Conscious Buyer	Compulsive Buyer	Impulsive Buyer	Normal Buyer		
Male	22 (16.3%)	63 (46.7%)	27 (20.0%)	23 (17.0%)	135 (100.0%)	4.077 (0.253)
Female	14 (10.9%)	56 (43.8%)	38 (29.7%)	20 (15.6%)	128 (100.0%)	
Total	36 (13.7%)	119 (45.2%)	65 (24.7%)	43 (16.3%)	263 (100.0%)	

Denote: *5% level of Significant and ()denotes percentage

The above table shows that compulsive buyers are equal in numbers. The study found that 51.33% of consumers are male and 48.67% consumers are female.

Since the p-value is larger than 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted at 5% level of significance. Hence it is concluded that there is no association between gender and online consumer compulsive buying behavior the calculated chi-square value is 4.077.

Association between age and E-shopping compulsive buying

H0: There is no association between the age and E-shopping compulsive buying behaviors

Table 3: Association between age and E-shopping compulsive buying

Age Group	Consumer Type				Total	Chi-Square Value (P-Value)
	Brand Conscious Buyer	Compulsive Buyer	Impulsive Buyer	Normal Buyer		
Below 25 years	30 (18.1%)	66 (39.8%)	41 (24.7%)	29 (17.5%)	166 (100.0%)	17.847 (0.007)*
Between 26 - 40 years	4 (5.0%)	46 (57.5%)	22 (27.5%)	8 (10.0%)	80 (100.0%)	
Above 40 years	2 (11.8%)	7 (41.2%)	2 (11.8%)	6 (35.3%)	17 (100.0%)	
Total	36 (13.7%)	119 (45.2%)	65 (24.7%)	43 (16.3%)	263 (100.0%)	

*Denote: 5% level of Significant and ()denotes percentage

The study found that 166 of a consumer are below 25years, 80 consumers are between 26years-40years, and 17 consumers are above 40years.

Since the p-value is less than 0.01 the null hypothesis is rejected at 1% level of significance. Hence it is concluded that there is no association between the age of consumers and e-shopping compulsive buying. The age group below 25years is 25.09%, 26-40years group is 17.49% and above 40years is 15.20%, the study found out that most of the compulsive buyers are below the above group of 25years.

Suggestions

- The marketers should focus their attention and also the sellers should provide EMI Facilities to the buyers.
- A Consumer can avoid often going for shopping.
- The Consumer can make a list before going shopping.
- The Shopper can reduce the usage of credit cards.
- Respondents can avoid clicking at online ads which are placed on social networks.
- Consumers should start to buy their products with self-control
- E-shoppers can seek some assistance from their family members and friends. Respondents can engage themselves by doing some other work instead of going shopping as hobby.

Managerial Implications

The changeability of promotional reply is different in retail markets, channels and outlets would be analyzed for the creation of required modifications in the course of delivery of advertising programs to the customers. The study shows that the sellers can quintessence on psychological factors of consumers. In which consumers are easily influenced in compulsive buying. Marketers can focus on both male and female. Both are equally participated in compulsive buying. But as per the study, the most of the compulsive buyers are at the age of below 25 years. So here the marketer can concentrate on students and youngsters. Private employees are highly involved in compulsive buying. So the marketer can place a shop near to the private companies. Most of the buyers are unmarried. And those consumers are highly involved in unwanted purchase which was upload to purchase addiction. Here the buyers would like to buy the smart phones according to the updated version in the market. So the marketers should target these types of customers to promote sales. And also window shopping plays a major role in compulsive buying. And the offers and advertisements play a vital role in e-shopping compulsive buying behavior. So here marketer should give attractive ads and must provide offers like discount sales, year end sales, and coupons, etc. The main reason for e-shopping compulsive buying is where the marketer can create a page in social networks, online advertisements, and attractive web designs are can be used to influence the compulsive buyer. The other factors are also branded goods, celebrations, packing, and culture. The marketer can also cover the customer through packaging by using attractive wrappers and slogans. These are some of the factors where a marketer can influence the compulsive buyers and promote sales towards compulsive buying.

Conclusion

The study conducted on the topic “A STUDY ON E-SHOPPING COMPULSIVE BUYING BEHAVIOUR”. The research shows that the male and female customers are equal in number on e-shopping compulsive buying behavior. The study also states that most of the compulsive buyers are unmarried and also they are educated. As per the occupation is concerned the most of the compulsive buyers are working people. Especially private employees are highly involved in compulsive buying. The most of the compulsive buyers are the middle-class family and upper middle-class. It is also said that most of the compulsive buyers family type are nuclear family. The factors influencing the compulsive buying are considered in the research are the psychological factors, credit facility, product factor, and cultural factors. Most influencing factor in the study is psychological factor. This is the ultimate reason which pushes the buyers to buy the product under compulsion. And the second most influencing factors are credit facility. And it is followed by product factors and online shopping factors. And the least factor is cultural factors. Therefore it states that the compulsive buying behavior are becoming common and also the marketers can

promote the sales by knowing the customer shopping attitudes and they can also concentrate factors influencing consumer which to endorse the benefit to the marketers.

Limitations of the Study

- The data from the sample may not reflect the universe. Therefore researcher considered two hundred and sixty three samples and there was also a time limit for doing the dissertation.
- The study did not go for in-depth testing of the tools due the inadequacies of tools.

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